

Centrifuge Modeling Investigation of Geosynthetic-reinforced and Pile-supported Embankments

Abstract

Geosynthetic-reinforced and pile-supported embankments (GRPSE) encompass two core components of the above-reinforced embankments and the underlying composite foundation.

In the centrifuge modeling of GRPSE, simplifying or omitting the key aspects related to the core components can weaken the similarity of working performance between models and prototypes. In the current study, to investigate the effects of the change of pile arrangement

on the overall working mechanism of GRPSE, two groups of centrifuge model tests on

GRPSE (Groups A and B with different pile cap sizes and spacings) were conducted with the similarity design of materials, geometry, and pile-soil friction taken into account. The test

models involve the embankment slope, geotechnical reinforcement, large-diameter and cast-in-situ concrete pipe (PCC) piles and soft soil foundation. It is verified that increasing

the area replacement ratio through expanding the pile-cap area and enlarging the pile spacing is an economical way to reduce the final settlement and post-settlement, allowing for more

loading to be concentrated on the PCC piles with a lower pile-soil stress ratio. Additionally, the influences of the 1g model preparation and g-ring loading method are analyzed and

discussed. The subsurface settlements during the embankment loading stage, as well as the total rebound deformation, were recorded, and it is found that, based on the four-stage global

settlement characteristics investigation, the settlement in the embankment construction stage and the final settlement are both overestimated. This study provides essential insights into the

22 influence of modeling stress history on the deformation in centrifuge testing and serves as a
23 reference for the pile arrangement design of GRPSE.

24 **Author keywords:** Geosynthetic-reinforced and pile-supported embankments; Centrifuge
25 modeling; 1g model preparation; Settlement; Rebound.

26

27 **1. Introduction**

28 Embankment construction over soft foundations is a challenging problem for geotechnical
29 engineers due to the undesirable characteristics of soft soils, such as low bearing capacity and
30 over settlements. Geosynthetic-reinforced and pile-supported embankments (GRPSE) is a soft
31 ground improvement method collaborating a base-strengthened embankment and an
32 underlying composite foundation enhanced by (capped) piles ([Girout et al. 2015](#)).
33 Well-designed GRPSE can ensure global stability, controlled post-settlement and reasonable
34 economic performance ([Jiang et al. 2022](#)). Hence, it is considered to be a reliable solution
35 suitable for time-bound construction project foundations on soft soils, especially for newly
36 built or widen embankments ([Van Eekelen et al. 2015](#)). However, the working mechanisms
37 of GRPSE with large-diameter and cast-in situ concrete pipe (PCC) piles still needs to be
38 investigated.

39 By deliberately increasing the standard earth gravity, g , by a factor N , centrifuge modeling
40 makes it possible to study a $1/N$ small-scale model with the same stress and deformation levels
41 as a full-scale prototype ([Schofield 1980](#)). It is highly meaningful to explore the behavior of
42 GRPSE using centrifuge modeling techniques and further deepen the theoretical and practical
43 studies of GRPSE. Previously, many centrifuge modeling tests on GRPSE were reported to
44 investigate the load transfer mechanisms, pile-soil interactions, and deformation characteristics.
45 The former studies considered the material properties (subsoil, fill material and geosynthetic
46 reinforcement), the geometry of the embankment and pile layout, and even the velocity of
47 field construction and drainage conditions ([Blanc et al. 2013](#); [Ye et al. 2015](#); [Shen et al. 2019](#);

48 [Wu et al. 2021](#)). Based on the aforementioned existing researches, some remarkable techniques
49 of GRPSE centrifuge modeling in pile modeling, subsoil modeling and embankment
50 construction simulation are summarized as follows:

51 (1) For pile modeling in GRPSE centrifuge tests, since both the diameter of modeling
52 piles and the spacing between them are quite small after scaling for the condition of group piles,
53 it's usually difficult for the model to contain the same number of piles as in prototype without
54 disturbing the modeling soil foundation. To solve this issue, [Lally and Naughton \(2012\)](#)
55 simplified the 3D problem into 2D by using pile walls, and [Ye et al. \(2015\)](#) reduced the number
56 of modeling piles by enlarging their diameter with an equal substitution rate. However, either
57 reducing the dimension of the problem or the number of piles, the form of the composite
58 foundation is changed. To accurately simulate the mechanical behavior of GRPSE, the
59 geometric layout of the piles in the centrifugal modeling needs to be consistent with that in the
60 real composite foundation. Concerning the construction of model piles, the equipment has very
61 rigorous requirements as it will work in a high-gravity field. The installation of piles in the
62 GRPSE centrifuge modeling should be conducted under 1g condition ([Li et al. 2018](#)) as it
63 effectively reduces the disturbance of soil during pile installation and makes the modeling
64 process similar to the in-situ operation.

65 (2) For subsoil modeling in GRPSE centrifuge tests, it is of high importance to ensure that
66 the physical properties of the remoulded samples are equivalent to those in situ. The support
67 and consolidation of subsoil have a vital influence on the working mechanism of GRPSE
68 ([King et al. 2021](#)). The simulation of the settlement process of fictional soft soil can be done

69 with a controllable rigid mobile tray which moves downwards (Fagundes et al. 2017; Girout et
70 al. 2018). Materials of alternative replacement for soft soil include synthetic sponge (Lally and
71 Naughton 2012) and expanded polystyrene (Ellis and Alsam 2009), the use of which makes it
72 possible to speed up or artificially control the settlement velocity of soft subsoil between piles.
73 Most recently, the working mechanisms for the ultimate limit state of the GRPSE as well as
74 the long-term condition with the consolidation of soft soil have gained increasing concerns
75 (Zhuang et al 2021; King et al. 2021), and in addition to the above-mentioned methods, more
76 alternative measures were adopted.

77 (3) About the simulation of embankment construction in centrifuge tests for GRPSE, it is
78 common in practice for the embankments to be constructed in stages. The centrifugal loading
79 methods usually employed include: (a) G-rising method. In this method, the embankment
80 model is constructed at 1g. Subsequently, a stepwise increase in centrifugal acceleration is
81 applied to simulate the in-situ loading (Ellis and Aslam 2009; Wang et al. 2014a; Zhang et al.
82 2018; Chen et al. 2022). (b) In-flight loading method. This method of pouring sand in flight
83 provides a realistic strategy for embankment construction. However, its utility is constrained
84 by the equipment and as such, the available reports on this technique are limited. (Reshma et al.
85 2020; Xiao et al. 2022). Alternatively, with the aid of a manipulator, it is possible to apply the
86 same load to the items (such as steel plates and water tanks) in embankment modeling, during
87 in-flight construction (Okuyay et al. 2014; Girout et al. 2018). (c) Combined loading method.
88 The staged construction is simulated using 1g filling and in-flight loading methods with a
89 hydraulic jack (Ye et al. 2015) or gasbag loading device (Yu et al. 2021). Although the method

90 of equivalent loading avoids the problem of geometric dissimilarity during the centrifuge
91 acceleration process, the replacement of the embankment material increases the uncertainty
92 regarding the arching effect in soil.

93 The majority of existing centrifuge studies on GRPSE provide fundamental insights into
94 its working mechanism, but some of the key aspects of GRPSE are either simplified or omitted.
95 Some common simplifications and omissions include: (a) simplifying the geometric
96 arrangement of the composite foundation with group piles; (b) not including or simulating the
97 subsoil with mechanical devices or material substitutes; and (c) replacing the embankment
98 with equivalent loads or large area surcharges. It should be noted that the performance of the
99 GRPSE system is dominated by the above-reinforced embankments and the underlying
100 composite foundation. The aforementioned simplifications and omissions in the centrifugal
101 tests can significantly weaken the similarity of the modeling system and prototype, and thus
102 influence the accuracy of the experimental studies. Therefore, it is crucial to accurately model
103 the geometric characteristics, mechanical properties and geological conditions of GRPSE.

104 In this study, in order to better understand the behavior of GRPSE with PCC piles, two
105 groups of centrifugal model tests were designed and carried out. The effect of pile arrangement
106 on the overall working mechanism is studied, without the simplifications or omissions of the
107 main affecting factors, using the similarity simulation of material, geometry, and pile-soil
108 friction. Investigations are conducted into the characteristic behaviors of the subsurface
109 settlement, section deformation, stress distribution, load transfer and excess pore pressure. The
110 influences of the preparation for the 1g model and the g-rising embankment loading are

111 discussed.

112 **2. Centrifugal Modeling and Preparations**

113 *Model Description*

114 The current study was performed in the TLJ-60A geotechnical centrifuge at Nanjing Hydraulic
115 Research Institute (Fig. 1), which has a nominal radius of 2.0 m with a maximum acceleration
116 of 200 g and a payload capacity of up to 300 kg. The model tests were conducted in a top-open
117 rectangular strongbox with the inside dimensions of 700 mm (length) \times 350 mm (width) \times 450
118 mm (height). The primary material utilized in the strongbox is stainless steel, except for the
119 front side where a transparent plexiglas plate is employed to facilitate deformation testing.

120

121 **Fig. 1 Photo of the TLJ-60A geotechnical centrifuge at Nanjing Hydraulic Research Institute**

122 As shown in Fig. 2a, the prototypical height of the embankment is 6.0 m, and the
123 thicknesses of the top soft stratum and the underlying stratum are 9.6 m and 9.0 m,
124 respectively. Embankments were constructed on the soft foundation reinforced by PCC piles
125 following Liu et al. (2009). The PCC piles utilized in the study have an outer diameter of 1.20
126 m and a length of 12.0 m. The pile toes penetrate through the soft clay stratum and terminate
127 at a depth of 2.4 m into the underlying clay stratum. As such, the embankment in this study is

128 founded on floating piles (King et al. 2019). To study the effects of the change of pile layout
 129 on the working mechanism of GRPSE, two groups (A and B) of piles were studied with the
 130 PCC piles installed in rectangular patterns for both groups, and the pile spacings are 3.48 m
 131 and 4.20 m for Group A and Group B, respectively. The area replacement ratio of pile caps
 132 for GRPSE are 9.3% for Group A, and 18.6% for Group B, which are within the typical range
 133 of 5-30% (Han 2015). The gravitational acceleration is taken as 60g (scaling factor $N = 60$),
 134 and the dimensions of the components in the centrifuge models are reduced accordingly as
 135 shown in Fig. 2b. Note that only half of the GRPSE system was built in this centrifugal model
 136 due to symmetry (Yu et al. 2021). The geometric parameters of the prototypical cases and the
 137 centrifugal models are shown in Table 1. Table 2 presents the material parameters.

138 **Fig. 2 Schematic of GRPSE: (a) Prototype profile; (b) Centrifugal model**

139 ***Rigid Pile Foundation Modeling***

140 **Soft foundation preparation**

141 To minimize the vertical friction between the soil and the inside wall of the strongbox, a thin
 142 film of silicone grease was applied on its inside vertical surfaces. Subsequently, the slurry

143 was de-aired with a water content twice that of its liquid limit and then pre-consolidated with
 144 staged pressure in the strongbox. After the preparation of the underlying silty clay, the soft
 145 layer was constructed. The soft stratum and underlying stratum in the centrifugal model
 146 foundation were constructed using dredged marine clay and silty clay obtained from
 147 Lianyungang Port, respectively.

148 **Subsoil modeling**

149 The effective geostatic stress in the prototype ($\sigma'_v(z)$) can be calculated using Eq. (1):

$$\sigma'_v(z) = \begin{cases} 9.3z, & 0 \leq z \leq 9.6 \\ 89.28 + 10.2(z - 9.6), & 9.6 < z \leq 18.6 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

150 where z is the depth from the surface in the prototype. This foundation model was prepared
 151 in the consolidator strongbox at 1g, and the effective vertical consolidation stress of each layer
 152 is uniform and equal to the top pressure, P' , upon completely consolidated. Based on the
 153 principle of achieving an equal overall average degree of consolidation with the self-weight
 154 consolidated soil layer at a centrifuge acceleration of 60 g, \bar{U} is given in Eq. (2),

$$\bar{U} = \frac{\int_0^H P' dz}{\int_0^H \sigma'_v dz} = 1.0 \quad (2)$$

155 where H is the total thickness of strata. Finally, the top pressures P' at 1g are determined as
 156 57.6 kPa and 115.2 kPa using Eq. (3) for the soft stratum and the underlying stratum (Fig. 3),
 157 respectively.

$$P' = \begin{cases} 57.6 \text{ kPa}, & 0 \leq z \leq 9.6 \\ 115.2 \text{ kPa}, & 9.6 < z \leq 18.6 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

158
159 **Fig. 3 Equivalent effective stress of vertical consolidation (in prototype scale)**

160 **Pile Modeling**

161 The model piles were fabricated from hollow cylindrical aluminium (Al) tubes with an outer
 162 diameter of 200 mm and thickness of 1.0 mm, which simulated the in-situ PCC piles with an
 163 outer diameter of 1.20 m and thickness of 0.15 m according to the similarity of compression
 164 stiffness. The model piles penetrate through the whole soft layer and are embedded into the
 165 underlying stratum at a depth of twice its diameter, 40 mm. The diameter and thickness of the
 166 pile cap (also in Al) for the Group A model are 20 mm and 4 mm, respectively. For Group B
 167 model, the above-mentioned dimensions are 34 mm and 5 mm, respectively. The caps were
 168 not coated with sand since the surface of an in-situ cap is not as rough as the PCC piles below
 169 it. It should be noted that the layouts of the model piles were configured to be identical to
 170 those in the prototypes.

171 The test pile was initially affixed with strain gauges on the external surfaces, and
 172 subsequently coated with epoxy resin to provide a waterproof layer. Note that it is important
 173 to allocate careful consideration to the interface similarity that exists between the cast-in-situ

174 PCC piles and the surrounding soil. To achieve a comparable surface roughness to actual
175 PCC piles, a uniform coating of sand was applied to both the interior and exterior surfaces of
176 the Al tubes utilizing adhesive agents. This coating process ensures a consistent and even
177 distribution of sand throughout the Al tubes. Interface properties are introduced later in the
178 section of “Testing Methods”.

179 The installation of piles under 1g field is a crucial step to achieve satisfactory modeling
180 for the pile group of the composite foundation. After the preparation of the subsoil under
181 consolidation stress, the pressure was removed. To reduce the swelling effect in 1g piling, pile
182 holes with a diameter identical to that of the model piles were drilled before installing the
183 Aluminum tubes. Sampling of the pile holes was performed using a thin-wall sampling pipe,
184 along with a vertical orientation guide and a vent pipe which has chipping at the bottom. The
185 sampling process was done in four steps: (a) slowly inserting the thin-wall sampling pipe with
186 the guide into the pile position depth; (b) sinking the vent pipe to a position near the inner wall
187 of the sampling pipe; (c) cutting off the soil at the bottom with the chipping by turning the vent
188 pipe; and (d) gently withdrawing the sampling pipe with the aid of venting to avoid shrinkage
189 of the hole. Thereafter, The Al tube was installed precisely to the design position using a
190 specialized beam and a fixed-length driver. Finally, the hollow model pile was filled
191 meticulously with the soil from within the sampling pipe. The installation of each PCC model
192 pile was completed through three sequential stages: sampling, piling, and backfilling. This
193 modified method enables the modeling of the pile group of the entire foundation with high
194 efficiency and minimal disturbance for soil and piles. To reduce potential gaps between the

195 piles and the underlying subsoil, pre-consolidation was carried out for 1.5 hours under a 60g
196 acceleration.

197 *Geosynthetic-reinforced Embankment Modeling*

198 Previous studies often simplified the GRPSE embankment as a uniform load on the subsoil,
199 instead of modeling it as a slope (Ed Ellis 2009; McGuire and Filz 2017; Girout et al. 2018;
200 King et al. 2019; da Silva Burke and Elshafie 2020). This simplification may arise unsimilarity
201 between the model and the prototype. In the current study, to avoid the above-mentioned
202 problem, an embankment with a slope ratio of 1 vertical unit to 1.5 horizontal units
203 (1.0V:1.5H) is included. The embankment filling material was obtained by mixing silty sand
204 and iron-ore particles with a weight ratio of 2.4:1.0. The dry density of the mixed material is
205 2.08 g/cm³, and the design filling density is 1.97 g/cm³, with the relative density being 0.95.
206 The filling material was placed and compacted in ten lifts using a mass-volume control
207 method after the pre-consolidation of the composite foundation. The average grain size of the
208 mixed embankment fill falls within the range of 0.18 mm to 0.25 mm. The ratio of pile
209 diameter to average grain size exceeds 136, indicating that the scale effect would be
210 negligible (Blanc et al. 2013). A screen mesh with an aperture size of 1.0 mm × 1.0 mm was
211 utilized to simulate a geogrid commonly observed in the fields. This screen mesh has the
212 equivalent ultimate tensile stiffness in both longitudinal and transverse directions with the
213 prototype (with the value of 3.5 kN/m at a strain of 2%, which corresponds to 210 kN/m in
214 the prototype). In the centrifugal test, the screen mesh was placed on the top surface of the
215 pile cap.

216 Due to the necessity of constructing the embankment under 1g condition, the
217 construction process of the embankment was simulated using the "g-rising" method, which
218 gradually increases the acceleration to prevent undrained damage. The centrifugal
219 acceleration was increased linearly from 1g to 60g over 120 min (equivalent to 100 d in the
220 prototype by multiplying the square of the scaling factor). With the g-rising method, the
221 behavior of the model remains consistent across different g-levels when considering the ratios
222 of various dimensions (Ellis and Aslam 2009).

223 *Testing Methods*

224 **Direct shear tests for interface properties**

225 To obtain the properties of the interfaces between (a) the surface-roughened Al model pile
226 and the soft soil, (b) the surface-roughened Al model pile and the underlying stratum, and (c)
227 the Al cap and the embankment filling, direct shear tests were conducted according to Jiang
228 et al. (2020). Following the Mohr-Coulomb model, the shear interface friction angles
229 (denoted as δ) associated with the shear interface between the sand-coated Al plate and the
230 soft soil, as well as the sand-coated Al plate and the underlying soil, were determined to be
231 25° and 30°, respectively. The angle between the Al plate and the embankment filling was
232 33°. The ratios of δ and effective internal friction angle (denoted as ϕ') of the above tests
233 satisfy that $0.7 < \delta/\phi' < 1.0$, which implies that the simulation of pile-soil contact in the
234 centrifugal model tests falls within the range of standard working conditions (Nunez et al.
235 2013).

236 **Deformation testing**

237 Two sets of tests were arranged to measure the subsurface settlements. One is for the settlement
238 at the central section of the road, while the other is for the shoulder section, as shown in Fig. 4.
239 A laser ranging sensor was employed to measure the vertical displacements of the pile top and
240 the soil between the piles on the surface of the composite foundation beneath the embankment.
241 The sensor was affixed to the top of the model box using a bracket. The chassis of the
242 self-made nylon column settlement mark was positioned at the measurement point. And the top
243 laser reflector was linked to the slender nylon column passing through the embankment.
244 During the tests, the real-time distance between the sensor and the reflector was measured to
245 obtain the settlement of the measurement point. Besides, the transparent plexiglass wall of the
246 model box can be disassembled to allow for the placement of the flexible grids horizontally
247 and vertically on the front surface of the composite foundation.

248 **Vertical stress testing**

249 Fig. 4 presents the plan views of the layout of piles and the arrangement of
250 instrumentation by taking Group A as an example, and the situation of Group B is similar.
251 For a central pile and a shoulder pile, the soil pressure cells were placed on the top of the pile
252 cap and at the soil centroid among the piles to measure the variations in the vertical stress.
253 The earth pressure cell has a diameter of 12 mm, and its accuracy error is within 0.3% of the
254 full scale. Before the test, all the earth pressure cells were calibrated with embankment soil in
255 the high-gravity field following [Jiang et al. \(2020\)](#). Additionally, the axial forces acting on
256 the pile shaft at various depths were measured using the calibrated strain gauges attached to
257 the external side of the test pile. Pore water pressure was also measured using pre-buried

258 micro pore pressure gauges to analyze the consolidation condition.

259

260 **Fig. 4 Plan view of pile layout and earth pressure cells on the subsurface**

261 **Testing stages**

262 The centrifuge testing process has four stages, each initiates at a specific phase of
263 centrifugal acceleration. These stages involve: (a) the Acceleration Stage to linearly increase
264 the gravitational acceleration from 1g to 60g which begins at the start of testing and lasts until
265 T_1 , which is equivalent to the embankment loading stage; (b) the Consolidation Stage from T_1
266 to T_2 , during which the centrifuge model is held at a constant acceleration of 60g; (c) the
267 Deceleration Stage from T_2 to T_3 to reduce the acceleration to 1g; and (d) the Static Stage in
268 which the centrifuge is held at a gravitational acceleration of 1g until finishing data
269 acquisition. To obtain a comprehensive understanding of settlement characteristics, ongoing
270 settlement monitoring was conducted since the deceleration (T_2) of the centrifuge.

271 **3. Results**

272 *Subsurface Settlement Analysis*

273 **Central soil settlement**

274 The acceleration history of the centrifuge and the settlement history at the central section of
 275 the GRPSE model throughout the testing process are shown in Fig. 5. The settlement of soil
 276 in the subsurface exhibits an almost linear increase during the Acceleration Stage, in which
 277 the settlement reaches 9.1 mm (546 mm in prototype) for Group A and 8.2 mm (492 mm in
 278 prototype) for Group B. Subsequently, in the Consolidation Stage, the rate of settlement
 279 growth slows down over time. The settlement increment of this stage is mainly due to the
 280 drainage consolidation, which is 3.4 mm (204 mm in prototype) for Group A and 2.6 mm
 281 (156 mm in prototype) for Group B. As such, the maximum settlements for Groups A and B
 282 are 12.5 mm (750 m in prototype) and 10.8 mm (648 mm in prototype), respectively.

283 **Fig. 5 Settlement of the central soil of GRPSE model: (a) Group A; (b) Group B**

284 Whilst in the Deceleration Stage of the centrifuge, the foundation exhibits significant
 285 rebound as shown in Fig. 5. Even during the Static Stage, the composite foundation continues
 286 to rebound albeit at a noticeably reduced rate. Throughout the monitoring duration, the
 287 combined foundation rebound for Group A and Group B is 6.3 mm (378 mm in prototype)
 288 and 5.0 mm (300 mm in prototype), respectively, equal to 69.2% and 61.0% of the maximum

289 settlement. This phenomenon indicates that the settlement observed during the Acceleration
290 and Consolidation Stages is a result of combined elastic-plastic deformation, consisting of
291 both the volumetric deformation and the drainage consolidation.

292 The duration required for the in-situ construction of the embankment is 100 d, as
293 determined by integrating the model similarity ratio during the Acceleration Stage (2 h from
294 the start to T_1). The settlement rate of the soil located between the piles experiences a
295 substantial decline during the Consolidation Stage, and the ultimate settlement has not been
296 reached at the end of the stage (T_2). By considering T_1 as the reference zero point, the
297 ultimate settlement (S_∞) of the Consolidation Stage can be estimated in the local coordinate
298 system by assuming that the relative settlement (S_t) and relative consolidation time (t) have
299 a hyperbolic correlation as shown below:

$$S_t = \frac{t}{\alpha + t} S_\infty \quad (4)$$

300 Derivated from Eq. (4), a linear relationship between t/S_t and t (Wang et al. 2014b)
301 can be obtained:

$$\frac{t}{S_t} = \frac{1}{S_\infty} t + \frac{\alpha}{S_\infty} \quad (5)$$

302 where α is a parameter of the intercept (α/S_∞) which can be calculated from the relative
303 settlement data in the Consolidation Stage by taking T_1 as the original time point. S_∞ can
304 then be obtained as the inverse of the slope ($1/S_\infty$) of the fitting straight line. The fitting lines
305 for Groups A and B are shown in Fig. 6.

306 The settlement of the subsurface soil at the central section of GPRSE of Group A and
307 Group B in the embankment filling stage is 544 mm and 489 mm in the prototype scale

308 respectively. Using the above-mentioned hyperbolic method, The settlement during the
 309 Consolidation Stage for Group A and Group B in the prototype scale is 256 mm and 209 mm,
 310 respectively. And the total (ultimate) settlement of the two groups is 800 mm and 698 mm,
 311 respectively. This implies that the post-settlement of both groups is well controlled within 50
 312 mm if taking T_2 as the beginning of the embankment service. Hence, the settlement in the
 313 Acceleration Stage accounts for 68.0% of the ultimate settlement for Group A and 70.1% for
 314 Group B. After the Deceleration Stage, the degree of consolidation of Group A is deduced to
 315 be 93.8%, and 93.1% for Group B. The above results are shown in Table 3.

317 **Fig. 6. Prediction of subsurface soil settlement at the central line of GRPSE in the Consolidation**
 318 **Stage (in prototype scale)**

319 Through the comparison of the above results between the two groups, the pile
 320 arrangement of Group B is more effective with respect to the control of soil settlement. Thus,
 321 Group B is of more interest in the current study. For Group B, the pile-soil settlement
 322 relationship at both the central and shoulder sections is analyzed with the laser displacement
 323 sensor positioned at the pile top. As shown in Fig. 7, there does not appear to be an obvious

324 variation in pile settlements between the central and shoulder sections, nor is there a
325 significant difference in the soil settlement between the two sections observed in the
326 subsurface. The pile settlement and soil settlement of the central section only become slightly
327 higher than those of the shoulder section. Based on the previously determined degree of
328 consolidation, the predicted ultimate settlement values for the central pile, shoulder soil, and
329 shoulder pile are 559 mm, 682 mm, and 526 mm, respectively. Hence, the residual settlement
330 after the embankment filling is 178 mm for the central pile, 188 mm for the shoulder soil and
331 139 mm for the shoulder pile. Similarly, for Group A, the ultimate settlement of the shoulder
332 soil can be computed as 813 mm, resulting in a post-settlement of 228 mm at the shoulder.

333 Based on the subsurface settlement analysis, it is demonstrated that Group B with a
334 larger pile diameter and pile spacing shows a better ability for settlement control. Even
335 though the pile spacing is increased from 3.48 m (Group A) to 4.20 m (Group B), Group B
336 can expand the pile cap area and increase the pile cap replacement ratio (m) to 18.6%, which
337 is twice that of Group A. As a result, the final predicted settlement on the subsurface in Group
338 B does not increase but instead decreases to 87.3% of that of Group A at the central section,
339 and 68.0% at the shoulder section. Therefore, expanding the area of the pile cap to increase
340 the area replacement ratio enables an increase in pile spacing, reducing the number of piles
341 accounted for by the composite foundation. This approach can reduce settlement and provide
342 an economic benefit.

343 **Differential settlement between pile and soil**

344 Fig. 7 shows that during the process of embankment loading (corresponding to the

345 Acceleration Stage of the centrifuge), the settlement of the soil between piles gradually
 346 becomes larger than that of the piles. This difference is calculated and presented in Fig. 8.
 347 After the embankment is fully loaded and the centrifuge acceleration reaches 60g at T_1 (100 d
 348 in prototype), the settlement difference between the pile and soil (Δ_s) for the central section
 349 and shoulder section of Group B is 109 mm and 107 mm, respectively. The predicted
 350 ultimate Δ_s of the central section is 139 mm, and 156 mm for the shoulder section (Table 3).
 351 The settlement of the central section is larger than that at the shoulder section, while the Δ_s
 352 at the central section is slightly smaller than that at the shoulder section. Note that the Δ_s of
 353 Group B is relatively small compared to its pile spacing of 4.20 m in the prototype. This is
 354 mainly due to the low shear strength of the bearing layer, which is only 23 kPa, and the weak
 355 bearing capacity of the floating pile at the tip. This finding of the current study is consistent
 356 with [Shen et al. \(2020\)](#), which stated that floating piles behave as rigid inclusions and form a
 357 composite foundation with the surrounding soil. This composite foundation shares the total
 358 load under an approximately equal-strain condition, resulting in a smaller settlement
 359 difference (Δ_s) on the subsurface.

Fig. 7. Subsurface settlement of Group B (in

Fig. 8. Differential settlement between pile and

prototype scale)

soil of Group B (in prototype scale)

360 *Sectional deformation Analysis*

361 After completion of the test, the plexiglass at the front of the model box was removed to
362 measure the grid coordinates. By comparing these coordinates with the initial values, a
363 section deformation vector map was obtained (see Fig. 9). For both tests of Groups A and B,
364 the saturated soft foundation experiences horizontal displacement when the embankment is
365 loaded, and the ground surface outside the slope heaved (smaller for Group B). The results of
366 the subsurface settlement (S), the horizontal displacement of the slope toe (H), the maximum
367 uplift outside the slope (V) and the ratio of H/S are shown in Table 3. The value of H/S is
368 an important index for evaluating embankment stability (Indraratna et al. 1992). The H/S
369 value is 0.40 for Group A and 0.33 for Group B. Note that the manual measurement of the
370 section deformation after shutdown of the centrifuge overestimates the horizontal
371 displacement as well as the out-of-slope uplift, underestimates the central soil settlement
372 based on Jiang et al. (2021). Hence, the in-flight H/S values of both groups are within the
373 critical value of 0.5 as recommended by Chai et al. (2002), suggesting that the slope stability
374 is well-controlled in this study.

(a)

(b)

375 **Fig. 9. Sectional deformation vector diagram after test (in model scale): (a) Group A; (b) Group B**

376 ***Pile-Soil Stress Distribution***

377 To illustrate the vertical soil pressure distribution, Fig. 10 presents the pressure values on the
378 top surface of the pile and subsoil. Soil pressure increases with the growth of acceleration in
379 the loading stage. At the moment of T_1 , the soil pressure on the pile top of Group A at the
380 central section and the shoulder section is 280 kPa and 302 kPa, respectively, while in Group
381 B, it is 234 kPa and 244 kPa at the central section and the shoulder section, respectively.
382 Meanwhile, in Group A, the vertical stress on the subsurface soil is 62 kPa and 105 kPa for
383 the central section and shoulder section, respectively, while Group B shows a vertical stress
384 of 92 kPa and 68 kPa for the subsoil at the central section and shoulder section, respectively.
385 During the drainage consolidation stage, the pressure on the pile top experiences an
386 increment. Comparing the results at the moment of T_2 with T_1 , the vertical stress at the pile
387 top of the central section increases by 14% and 36% in Group A and Group B, respectively.
388 At the shoulder section, the stress increase is 4% for Group A and 29% for Group B. For the
389 vertical stress on the subsoil between piles, in most of the cases, there is no significant change
390 observed during the period from T_2 to T_1 .

391 To analyze the stress ratio and the load ratio between the pile and soil, the situation at
392 the central section is taken as an example. As shown in Fig. 11, at T_1 , the pile-soil stress
393 ratio (n) of the central section is $n_A = 4.5$ for Group A and $n_B = 2.5$ for Group B. After
394 the drainage consolidation at the moment of T_2 , the ratio increases to $n_A = 5.1$ and
395 $n_B = 3.4$, respectively. From T_1 to T_2 , the increase in n values indicates that the rigid

396 piles gradually share more fraction of the load from the embankment, exhibiting a stress
397 transfer effect. At T_2 , $n_B = 3.4$ is smaller than $n_A = 5.1$, meanwhile, the pile-soil bearing
398 load ratio (N) of Group B ($N_B = 0.8$) is higher than that of Group A ($N_A = 0.5$). Therefore,
399 the stress concentration effect on the pile top of Group B is weaker than that of Group A, and
400 the bearing capacity of the pile in Group B is better exerted. The reason lies in the main
401 difference between the two groups, the pile arrangement (see Table 1 and Fig. 2). The
402 replacement ratio of pile cap (m) of Group A is 9.3%. By expanding the pile cap area,
403 although the pile spacing is increased in Group B, its m value becomes two times that of
404 Group A. Thus, again, it is proved to be economical to expand the pile cap area, and at the
405 same time increase the pile spacing and reduce the number of piles, which will not affect N
406 value. Note that n and N usually increases monotonically at the stage of embankment
407 loading (Liu et al. 2007; Nunez et al. 2013), while the curves of n and N in this test have
408 a trend of increasing-decreasing in Fig. 11. This trend is mainly influenced by the stress
409 history of the model during the preparation stage under 1g, which will be discussed later.

410 **Fig. 10. Soil pressure on subsurface (in prototype scale): (a) Group A; (b) Group B**

411

412

Fig. 11. Pile-soil stress ratio and load ratio of the central section (in prototype scale)

413

The Axial Force of the Pile Shaft

414

Taking Group B as an example, Fig. 12 illustrates the variation of the axial force in prototype

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scale along the depth of the pile shaft at the central sections of the embankment, which starts

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from 100 d when the embankment is loaded. Overall, the distribution of the axial force along

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the pile shaft shows an increasing-decreasing trend as the depth increases. The observed

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increase in the axial force with the depth in the shallow layer of the foundation suggests that

419

the surrounding soft soil experiences downward displacement relative to the pile.

420

Consequently, a negative frictional force exists on the pile side, resulting in the transfer of

421

additional load from the soil to the pile body. Upon reaching its maximum value, the axial

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force exhibits a decreasing trend with increasing depth, while the pile side experiences

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positive friction. This observation suggests that the rigid pile is capable of transferring the

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supplementary stress of the shallow soft soil in the foundation to the deeper layers, thereby

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optimizing the load distribution and consequently reducing the overall settlement. The neutral

426

plane is situated at the interface between the positive and negative frictional resistances,

427 representing the point of maximum axial force within the pile body and zero relative
 428 displacements between the pile and surrounding soil. Based on Fig. 12, it is shown that the
 429 neutral plane is located at 0.4 times the pile length and exhibits characteristics akin to floating
 430 piles, which is consistent with the findings reported by Ye et al. (2015). Over time, the axial
 431 force displays an obvious increase during the consolidation process, signifying the transfer of
 432 more loads to the pile body, which indicates that the stress concentration effect of the rigid
 433 pile becomes more pronounced with the passage of consolidating time. Therefore, the pile
 434 becomes increasingly effective in withstanding and distributing the load.

435 **Fig. 12. Axial force of central pile shaft along depth of Group B (in prototype scale)**

436 ***Pore Pressure Analysis***

437 The history of excess pore water pressure (Δu) measured by pore water pressure sensors
 438 buried 2.4 m (in prototype scale) is shown in Fig. 13. In the embankment loading stage, Δu
 439 increases with time and reaches the peak at T_1 , then it gradually dissipates with time in the

440 consolidation stage. At the central section, the Δu level of Group A (with a peak value of
 441 50.8 kPa) is lower than that of Group B (with a peak value of 68.3 kPa). Concerning the
 442 shoulder section, Δu is larger in Group A than in Group B, with the peak values at 38.4 kPa
 443 and 30.5 kPa, respectively. It can be seen that with larger pile spacing and m in Group B
 444 compared to Group A, the peak value of Δu at the shoulder section is reduced by 20.6%,
 445 which is beneficial to the slope stability.

446 **Fig. 13. Excess pore water pressure at depth of 2.4 m (in prototype scale): (a) central section; (b)**
 447 **shoulder section**

448 **4. Discussion**

449 The centrifuge modeling approach adopted in this paper incorporates all critical aspects of the
 450 GRPSE system, and underlines the similarity law of geometric characteristics, mechanical
 451 features as well as geological conditions. To the best of the authors' knowledge, due to
 452 limitations in the available technology for in-flight pile and embankment construction, no
 453 case currently exists that includes in-flight pile group driving and embankment filling. The 1g
 454 model preparation method (Wang et al. 2020; Xu et al. 2020; Zhang and Chian 2021; Zhang

455 [and Chian 2022](#)) and g-rising method ([Chen et al. 2022](#); [Yu et al. 2021](#); [Zhou et al. 2019](#);
456 [Zhang et al. 2018](#); [Wang et al. 2014a](#)), despite their limitations, continue to be utilized in
457 many reports due to their relative ease of implementation. This is also true for the current
458 study. Herein, further discussions are proposed to investigate the influences of model
459 preparation on the experimental outcomes. For this purpose, the rebound of the foundation
460 needs to be understood first.

461 In the Deceleration Stage, the centrifugal acceleration is gradually decreased from 60g to
462 zero, and the geostatic stress is gradually reduced. Meanwhile, the foundation experiences
463 rebound due to unloading. According to [Jiang et al. \(2021\)](#), the amount of the rebound can be
464 fitted using a 6th-order polynomial equation. Fig. 14 shows that the Deceleration Stage of
465 Group B (chosen to be analyzed with more interest due to better capability) spans 0.13 hour
466 (as marked by the grey dashed line in Fig. 14), during which the rebound amounts of the
467 central pile, central soil, shoulder pile, and shoulder soil are 3.1 mm, 3.3 mm, 3.1 mm, and
468 3.6 mm, respectively. The reasons for the foundation rebounds are not only due to a reduction
469 in the load on the overlying embankment but also a decrease in the weight of the composite
470 foundation itself.

471 Subsequently, the Static Stage lasts for 8 hours (Fig. 14). Although the total stress does not
472 change during this period, the foundation continues to rebound until the rebound amounts
473 gradually become unchanged. The final rebound amounts of central piles, central soil, shoulder
474 piles, and shoulder soil are 1.1 mm, 1.7 mm, 1.5 mm, and 1.9 mm, respectively. After the
475 centrifuge stops, the total stress of the model decreases to the lowest level, and negative excess

476 pore pressure generates in the foundation. The soft clay has a small permeability coefficient as
 477 presented in Table 2, and a high viscosity of bound water. Consequently, the migration and
 478 adjustment of soil particles in the soft clay occur at a relatively slow rate, implying that the
 479 sluggish rebound observed in the subsurface is primarily attributable to the rheological
 480 macroscopic behavior of the soft clay.

481 During the Deceleration Stage and Static Stage, the rebound amount of subsoil at the
 482 shoulder section is greater than that of the central section. This is also the case for the piles. On
 483 the other hand, the rebound values of subsoil between piles are slightly larger than that of piles
 484 in both sections, and their difference at the central section and shoulder section is 0.6 mm and
 485 0.9 mm, respectively.

487 **Fig. 14. Rebound deformation of Group B during the Deceleration Stage and Static Stage (in model**
 488 **scale)**

489 Certainly, the rebound also occurs when the pressure is removed at the end of the
 490 pre-consolidation stage. In the context of modeling embankment loading, the employment of
 491 the g-rising method introduces an additional factor to consider in the form of

492 rebound-recompression deformation of the composite foundation. This phenomenon, which
493 typically does not exist in actual projects, is an integral component of the total settlement of
494 the foundation. According to Table 3 and Fig. 14, (a) the settlement during the Acceleration
495 Stage of Group A accounts for 68.0% of the ultimate deformation, and this proportion for
496 Group B is 70.1%; and (b) the total rebound deformation of the central section of Group B is
497 43.0% of the ultimate deformation. However, due to the employed 1g model preparation and
498 g-rising loading method, it is reasonable to obtain a qualitative conclusion that the settlement
499 of the Acceleration Stage and the ultimate settlement mentioned above are somewhat
500 overestimated. Additionally, it should be noted that the section deformation shown in Fig. 9,
501 as measured at 1g, cannot be deemed as the exact deformation that occurs in the flight.
502 Similarly, as a result of the aforementioned 1g model preparation and g-rising loading method,
503 the n and N histories present fluctuations during the Acceleration Stage and ultimately
504 terminate at values below 5.0, as illustrated in Fig. 11. These findings are consistent with the
505 results reported by [Li et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Reshma et al. \(2020\)](#), which suggest that utilizing the
506 method of pile installation at 1g leads to a reduced load-carrying capacity of the pile group,
507 as well as overestimated soil deformations.

508 The preparation of a centrifuge model presents challenges in maintaining a consistent
509 centrifugal gravity field, which leads to a complex stress history of the model foundation. As
510 a result, this introduces uncertainties in the test results. Both the limitations arising from 1g
511 model preparation and the simulation technology used for embankment construction remain
512 unresolved issues that require further investigation in the future. Besides, numerical methods,

513 such as the mesh-based method (Tho et al. 2013; Yu et al. 2015) and the meshless method
514 (Bui et al. 2008; Li et al. 2023), can be introduced for centrifuge modeling to analyze and
515 optimize the experiments.

516 **5. Conclusions**

517 Taking into account the similarity simulation of materials, geometry, and pile-soil frictions,
518 two groups of GRPSE centrifugal models are designed and carried out, which involve
519 embankment slope, geotechnical reinforcement, piles and soft soil foundation. The
520 spatiotemporal characteristics of settlement deformation and stress distribution are
521 investigated, and the influence of pile arrangement on the overall working mechanism of
522 GRPSE is studied. The main conclusions are as follows:

523 (1) Expanding the pile-cap area to increase the area replacement ratio presents an
524 opportunity to reduce the number of piles (with larger spacing) required for the composite
525 foundation, which can be cost-effective for various reasons. Based on this case, this approach
526 has been shown to reduce both the settlement and post-settlement, concentrate more loading
527 on PCC piles with a reduced pile-soil stress ratio, and not adversely affect either the excess
528 pore water pressure or the lateral displacement of the foundation.

529 (2) The bearing stratum for PCC piles is composed of silty clay. The neutral plane of the
530 pile shaft is buried within a depth of 5.0 m in prototype, resulting in a relatively low
531 differential settlement and pile-soil stress ratio. As such, these piles exhibit characteristics
532 similar to those of floating piles, which demonstrates the validity and rationality of the
533 approach utilized in the test.

534 (3) The settlement characteristics of the centrifuge test (divided into four stages) are
535 analyzed. During the Acceleration Stage, Group A and Group B experience settlements that
536 account for 68.0% and 70.1% of the predicted ultimate deformation, respectively. Looking
537 into Group B which is of more interest due to its better capability in settlement control, the
538 total rebound deformation of the central section of Group B contributes to 43.0% of the
539 ultimate settlement. It is essential to consider the effect of modeling stress history,
540 particularly in the deformation analysis of centrifuge tests.

541 (4) Despite the findings of this research, there are still limitations that should be taken
542 into account. The use of 1g model preparation, including pile installation, and g-rising
543 loading methods in centrifuge modeling can lead to overestimation of settlement during the
544 embankment construction stage and the final settlement to a certain degree. Further research
545 is necessary to enhance the comprehension of the impact of 1g model preparation on
546 centrifuge modeling, and to advance the GRPSE centrifuge modeling technique by
547 integrating accurate system characteristics.

548 **Data Availability Statement**

549 The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding
550 author upon reasonable request.

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559

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Tables with Captions

Table 1. Geometric parameters of centrifugal model and prototypical case

Items	Group A in prototype	Group A in model size	Group B in prototype	Group B in model size
Embankment height	6.0 m	100 mm	6.0 m	100 mm
Thickness of soft soil	9.6 m	160 mm	9.6 m	160 mm
Thickness of underlying stratum	9.0 m	150 mm	9.0 m	150 mm
Center to center pile spacing	3.48 m	58 mm	4.20 m	70 mm
Diameter of pile cap	1.20 m	20 mm	2.05 m	34 mm
Replacement ratio of pile cap (m)	9.3%	9.3%	18.6%	18.6%
Diameter of pile	1.20 m	20 mm	1.20 m	20 mm
Length of pile	12 m	200 mm	12 m	200 mm
Thickness of pile	0.15 m	1.0 mm	0.15 m	1.0 mm

Table 2. Material parameters

Material	Prototype properties
PCC pile	$\gamma=24 \text{ kN/m}^3$, $E=30 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu=0.2$
Geosynthetic	$J_{2\%}=210 \text{ kN/m}$, $E=2 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu=0.3$
Soft soil	$\gamma=19.3 \text{ kN/m}^3$, $e_0=0.878$, $w_L=41\%$, $w_p=20\%$, $\phi' = 29^\circ$
Underlying soil	$\gamma=20.2 \text{ kN/m}^3$, $e_0=0.662$, $w_L=29\%$, $w_p=16\%$, $\phi' = 33^\circ$
Embankment fill	$\gamma=19.7 \text{ kN/m}^3$, $\phi' = 41^\circ$

Note: γ -unit weight; E -effective Young's modulus; ν -Poisson's ratio; e_0 -initial void ratio of soil; $J_{2\%}$ -ultimate tensile stiffness of geotechnical reinforcement at 2% strain; w_L -liquid limit water content; w_p -liquid limit water content; ϕ' = effective internal friction angle.

Table 3. Subsurface soil settlement at central section (in prototype scale)

Group	Loading stage settlement	Consolidation stage settlement	Test-ending settlement at T_2	Predicted ultimate settlement	Consolidation time	Consolidation degree
A	544 mm	256 mm	750 mm	800 mm	1050 d	93.8%
B	489 mm	209 mm	648 mm	698 mm	900 d	93.1%

Table 4. Section deformations (in model scale, unit: mm)

Items	<i>S</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>H/S</i>
Group A after test	5.0	2.0	3.0	0.4
Group B after test	6.0	2.0	1.0	0.33

S - Surface settlement at central line of embankment; *H* - Horizontal displacement of slope toe; *V* - Maximum uplift outside slope.